

TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY: ADDRESSING SEX DIFFERENCES IN CLINICAL ENVIRONMENTS

WHY SEX MATTERS IN MEDICINE

Males and females respond differently to medications due to physiologic, metabolic, and genetic factors. Nanotechnology applications in medicine have added a new aspect of complexity to assessing how sex affects nanoscale drugs in the body.

SEX DIFFERENCES IN NANOMEDICINE

Sex	Body Composition	Heart Rate Variability	Distribution	Absorption	Clearance
Male	Males' higher water content may increase the effectiveness of water-soluble drugs nanoparticles.	Men have a lower risk of arrhythmias	Men have higher nanoparticles distribution to the liver.	Faster digestion and transit times.	The clearance of nanoparticles is faster, which might reduce side effects, but may also reduce the effectiveness of treatments.
Female	Females' higher fat content may increase the effectiveness of lipid-soluble drugs nanoparticles.	Females have higher risk of arrhythmias	Females have higher nanoparticles distribution to the kidneys.	Slower digestion and transit times.	Nanoparticles stay in the body longer, expanding the therapeutic window but leading possibly to higher toxicity.

SEX AND SCIENCE

Low female participation in Clinical trials is still persistent today: Low recruitment of women is still a problem in industry clinical trials. Today, trial participation among women has increased, but they are often still underrepresented.

Challenges Limiting Diversity in Clinical Trials: There are a number of barriers that limit broader enrollment in clinical trials such as financial issues, study restrictions or childbearing potential.

Encouraging participation: In the past, drug development was a one-size-fits-all process. Adding a sex-informed perspective, however, increases rigor, promotes drug discovery, and expands relevance for nanotechnology research.

